

JEL Classification: K 19
SECTION: "LAW".

Mykytiuk Mykola

Doctor of Law, Associate Professor
Institute of Department of State Guard of Ukraine
of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv
e-mail: mmavinnicia@ukr.net
ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-1759-7312>

Zayats Roman

Doctor of Law, Associate Professor
Lviv University of Business and Law
ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-4726-6362>

Humin Oleksiy

Doctor of Law, Professor
Lviv Politechnic National University
ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8016-945X>

Plukar Volodymyr

PhD (Law), Associate Professor
European University
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9797-5944>

PLACE OF SECURITY IN THE STATE GOVERNANCE SYSTEM: LAW APPROACH

***Annotation.** The article deals with the problems of theoretical and applied aspects of state guard in the system of state governance in Ukraine. The study of the genesis of the emergence and establishment of state concludes that the institution of state leaders' guard has appeared since the formation of the state, the emergence of state leaders and the emergence of contradictions between them. It is substantiated that in the context of reforms implemented in Ukraine, the modern security service of state authorities and officials has been established. It is concluded that the state guard is carried out under the statutory tasks directly in the sphere of state security and in order to ensure state security, and therefore, in the context of the activity of the Department of State Guard of Ukraine (hereinafter DSGU), the necessity of coercive measures application for the DSGU is wider and may concern either the offenders as provided for law enforcement agencies, or other persons in the interests of state protection of public authorities and officials.*

***Key words:** state guard; state security of public authorities and officials; state leaders; state governance.*

1. Statement of the problem

The political and security situation being developed recently in the world around Ukraine, as well as in Ukraine itself, has shown that both the world and Ukrainian community faced substantially new challenges, dangers and threats requiring a radical change in previously developed mechanisms, means and approaches to further regulation of the functioning and ensuring the mankind.

The neglect of the generally accepted principles of world law and order previously concluded by various international agreements, cynical and decisive interference in the internal affairs of other states, undermining their security and neglect of their national interests is an incomplete list of the negatives that mankind now faces. Hybrid relations, hybrid conflicts, and the like became the daily norm of behavior of certain political players in the international arena. Disrespect for human life, human values, promotion of extremism and separatism etc. is an incomplete list of current threats for many countries.

Ukraine's ability to adequately respond to challenges and threats is affected by internal economic and social and political factors. Besides the negative social consequences, the country's economic and environmental crisis is aggravating; and innovation is not being implemented etc.

The complexity of research analysis in the field of state security lies primarily within the restricted access format, which was generally not available for wide-ranging discussion among scientists, experts and citizens.

Although, the society is growing demands for increasing transparency of the activities of the state special services and other entities providing national security, strengthening the system of civilian control over their activities, their main features should be influence and efficiency. Furthermore, taking into account the urgent need for systemic reform of the security and defense sector, a comprehensive and open discussion of the directions and ways of its reforming, including the Department of State Guard of Ukraine as its subject is of a great concern. In addition, a need to find new approaches, ideas, solutions and mechanisms for the effective implementation of state guard is essential.

The purpose of the study is to deepen the theoretical and methodological foundations of legal and managerial practices in the field of state guard. It should be carried out by a comprehensive analysis of the current state of functioning of state guard and its governance, as well as substantiation of conclusions and suggestions on ways of solving problems within the mentioned area.

2. The main material

The function of state governance is a social management, because it is carried out in a human society by people and towards people. Both the subject and the object of control are represented here by a person. Consequently, the human factor is the main and chief one in the governing systems operating in a social environment. The main categories of social governing are the subject, object, managerial influence, feedback, governing system. However, their content, forms and methods of influence, purpose of interaction, fundamental principles are completely different from technocratic and biological systems. All known categories acquire a particular expression in the social governance of people activity, their groups and interconnections.

Governance takes place in any society and practically in any human group. Depending on historical, environmental, political and other circumstances, its goals,

forms, methods may vary. The need for governing remains unchanged. The basis of the need for governing is a simple circumstance, at first glance, inherent in any human group. It is a cooperation of people inside the community. It is cooperation, a joint work for the achievement of specific goals that transforms individual persons into a team. The need for people in cooperation, joint activity, and joint work objectively evolves into the need for governing. At the same time, this necessity always arises within any variants of joint people activity. Governance is a means of ensuring joint activities i.e. a condition for its normal functioning.

Society as a whole is a result of joint people activity, and their cooperation. Moreover, in this sense, society is the highest form of collective labour people, and governance is an attribute of social life.

On the assumption of the above, we can assume that significant signs of social governance are:

- 1) social governance always available within a common people activity;
- 2) the main purpose of governance implying the regulatory influence on the behavior of participants in joint activities;
- 3) the functions of social governance (coordination, adjustment, planning, control, supervision, coercion) implemented within the framework of public relations;
- 4) governing relations due to social and governing influences, which are a kind of, firstly, social, and, secondly, volitional relations;

On the assumption of the above, we can formulate definitions of social governance.

Social governance is a kind of volitional activity expressed in purposeful and organizing influence carried out to ensure consistency and order of joint actions of people and their groups to solve effectively the problems facing them [1].

Social governance, as well as the whole complex of social relations is a versatile and multifaceted phenomenon. Governance can be carried out by both one person and a team of people. One can manage economics, socio-political, spiritual spheres, etc. Therefore, the study of social governance involves representatives of various branches of knowledge: economists, sociologists, philosophers, psychologists, lawyers. Different variants of its structure have been offered.

From the standpoint of legal science, it is reasonable to use the criterion of “priority of interests” as the basis of the initial approach to the structuring of social governance, since the latter is used as one of the criteria for the allocation of public and private law. On this basis, social governance can be divided into:

- a) governance carried out with the purpose of realization of public (general) interests or public administration;
- b) governance carried out in order to implement corporate interests, or corporate governance;
- c) governance carried out in order to realize its private interests, or private management.

The most distinguished legal concomitants of social governance are:

- administrative law for public administration;
- corporate law for corporate governance;
- civil law for private management.

First of all, we are interested in public administration, because it primarily concerns the functions of the state, which are carried out in the implementation of state guard.

Public administration consists of:

1) state governance where the subject is a state represented by the corresponding entities;

2) public governance where subjects are non-state entities.

Each of these types of governing activity is characterized by specific features excluding the possibility of their identification. The differences between them are due to the peculiarities of their organization, the nature of applied forms and the methods of influence.

Therefore, the subjects of state governance act on behalf of the state.

Decisions taken within this system are mandatory for all participants in public relations, including non-governmental organizations and formations; their activity has legal and powerful status and is provided by the force of state.

State governance as a component of the public one is a state function inherent in special organizational structures (bodies), and its array is a system of public administration. The system as a whole and each of its components separately, performing functions of state administration, act exclusively on behalf of the state.

The decisions they make are mandatory for all participants in public relations, including non-governmental organizations and formations. This system consists of two components:

a) state bodies, i.e. state-owned (for example, the ministry, local state administration);

b) non-state bodies that don't belong to the state.

The first entities in this system possess the main and leading place which array is an integral part of the state apparatus. These bodies employ state-paid civil servants. The latter may exercise state control only if the state delegates the relevant powers to them. Thus, delegated powers of the state executive authorities are performed by executive committees of local self-government bodies regulated by the relevant rules of the law [2].

As noted by the famous national scientist V. Kolpakov, state governance as a part of social public administration retains the characteristics of the latter. Simultaneously, it has numerous features that reflect its specificity and provide an opportunity to be determined as an independent form of governance.

These features are found in the main components of the public governance system (subject, object, management influence) and integrative properties that are inherent as system governance.

The main feature of the subject is that it is a state as a whole. It is represented in the governing process by a system of special, as a rule, state bodies. The peculiarities of these bodies as direct subjects of state governance are as follows:

- first, they are set by the state (at will of the state);
- secondly, they are endowed with powers of state;
- thirdly, they carry out administrative functions on behalf of the state.

The main feature of an object is that it is an organized entity as a whole. Direct objects affected by this or that particular entity are the public governing spheres responsible to it. The decisive peculiarities of managerial influence are its inherent state power character (it contains the state command obligatory to execute), which manifests itself in the legal, mainly administrative and legal form (the system of norms, system of acts related to their application, the set of powers of the governance process participants), and has a continuous character.

The main integrative quality of the system is the realization of the full range of national interests in the sphere of social governance. All the main components of public governance have a complex structure, i.e. they consist of separate parts. Therefore, it is a governing subsystem with special properties, place and role in the governance process.

State governance is one of the key components of the subject of administrative law. Taking into account the prolonged renewal of administrative law, especially in the conditions of the reforms carried out in the state, its methodological principles, the change of “state centered” ideology into “human centered”, the priority of the state service to a man (public service activities) are positive democratic achievements of Ukrainian society, and scientific awareness of these achievements.

The type of social governance as a state government realizes the powerful influence of the state, first of all, in its power influences. The main characteristic of state governance is the legitimacy of the state’s actions, and the non-fulfillment of those or other tasks underlying administrative influence legitimizes the right of the state to apply coercion.

The science of administrative law encompasses different approaches to the interpretation of the phenomenon of public governance.

Thus, state governance in its broad sense is a set of all kinds of state activity realized in the functioning of the bodies of all branches of state power and aimed at regulating social relations. It covers activities:

- bodies of executive power (at the expense of implementation of executive and regulatory activity aimed at implementation of the requirements of the legal norms);
- bodies of legislative and judicial power (at the expense of lawmaking and justice administration);
- other state bodies that do not belong to certain branches of government (the Prosecutor's Office, the Central Election Commission, the National Bank, etc.);
- non-state bodies (bodies of local authorities, public organizations) within the implementation of their powers delegated by the state.

State governance in the narrow sense is the executive and administrative activities of executive authorities and other bodies in terms of implementing their executive and administrative functions. Along with the executive authorities, public administration in its part also implements other bodies and officials such as the President of Ukraine, the Prosecutor General’s Office of Ukraine, non-state bodies while performing delegated powers, etc. [3].

It should be noted that in administrative law the state governance in the narrow sense is the main one, since it allows qualitatively to analyze the executive and regulatory activity of executive bodies (with the state governance as the main activity area), as well as internal organization within the framework of the functioning of other state bodies.

The theory of administrative law widely investigates the problem of attributes of state governance often referred to as its features.

Five signs are mostly distinguished:

- 1) executive and administrative (power) nature;
- 2) sublegislative;
- 3) scale and versatility;
- 4) hierarchy;
- 5) directly organizing nature.

There is another approach to determining the features of state governance. Thus, Y. Bytiak distinguishes the following features of state governance:

- national nature since it covers the most important aspects of the life of both the state and society;
- direction for the implementation of the Constitution and laws of Ukraine (sublegislative activity);
- legally and powerful, managerial nature;
- organizational content by means of which the regulation and coordination of the joint work of people is achieved;
- activity and purposefulness within direct objects of its influence in the field of economic, social, administrative and political construction;
- continuous and permanent implementation [4].

S. Stetsenko distinguishes the following main features of state governance:

- a power nature characterized by of certain powers delegated by the state;
- sublegislative nature i.e. activities in the field of state governance aimed at fulfilling the requirements of the law;
- scale manifesting itself in the managerial influence on the economy, social and cultural, administrative and political spheres;
- systemacy i.e. carried out constantly;
- subordination i.e. higher and lower functional units with a clear subordination and hierarchy in the system of bodies;
- a system of administrative coercion in cases of violation of the current legislation entrusted to the body within providing a state guard;
- controlled nature of activities due to the bodies that control and oversee the implementation of functions of state governance [5].

An important factor in understanding the essence of state governance is the awareness of its principles. These are the basic principles and laws of the governance which must meet the following requirements:

- comply with the norms of the current legislation;
- reflect the most important, key regularities of state governance;
- meet the goal of state governance.

Principles are encompassed in the Constitution of Ukraine [6] since any activity, and moreover, managerial, should have a certain basis. Therefore, the Constitution of Ukraine enables to attribute the principles of state governance to the following:

- responsibility of the executive authorities (officials) for the task entrusted to the person and the state (Articles 3, 17, 19 and others of the constitution of Ukraine). This means that the constitution ensures the ability of citizens to participate in the governing of state affairs, and equal access to the civil service, to service in local government bodies.

In accordance with the provisions of Article 40 of the Constitution of Ukraine, everyone has the right to submit individual or collective written appeals or to address in person to the bodies of state power, local self-government bodies, officials and officers obliged to consider these applications and to provide a reasoned answer in the manner prescribed by law term. The possibility of citizens to be a member of political party, to be a participant in political elections or to support any of the candidates is also determined.

It is worthwhile to point out that since 2005 (the enactment of the Code of Administrative Justice of Ukraine) [7] the citizens have a legitimate opportunity to

appeal to specialized judicial bodies (administrative courts) regarding the protection of their rights, freedoms and interests from violations of state authority, bodies of local self-government, officials and officers, other subjects in the process of exercising power governing functions.

In accordance with the provisions of Article 113 of the Constitution of Ukraine, the Government of Ukraine and the executive authorities are responsible to the President of Ukraine and the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, as well as they are under the control and accountable to the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. Relations between higher and lower executive bodies are carried out on the basis of subordination;

– the supremacy of law encompassed in Article 8 of the Constitution of Ukraine. According to this principle, the Constitution of Ukraine has the highest legal force and its norms are the norms of direct action. Laws of Ukraine and other normative and legal acts are adopted on the basis of the Constitution of Ukraine and must comply with it;

– the legitimacy following from the previous principle and is based on the provisions of the Constitution of Ukraine. The bodies of state power, officials and officers exercise their powers under the legal regime within the limits established by the Constitution and in accordance with the laws of Ukraine.

Lawfulness must be real, and reality is guaranteed by the duty of state bodies, officials and officers to obey the laws, responsibility to the Ukrainian people, as well as judicial control (including the Constitutional Court of Ukraine), prosecutorial supervision, control by special bodies of executive power (inspections, administrations, commissions, committees) and the right of citizens to appeal to state and public bodies, including the court.

Lawfulness as one of the most important principles of activity is stated in the normative documents determining the legal status of state governance subjects. One can distinguish the following features of this principle:

a) bodies (officials) carrying out public administration should adopt normative and legal acts that do not contradict the Constitution and laws of Ukraine;

b) law dominates the authorities disabling the officials to arbitrarily deal with an individual;

c) there are bodies that control and supervise the provision of state governance legality in the state;

– publicity, the real implementation of democratic transformations, the improvement of administrative processes in accordance with the requirements of documents on administrative reform, the provision in the state of genuine legality and real legal order is possible only under conditions of broad publicity and consideration of public opinion. This principle contains three interconnected and interdependent components:

– firstly, wide publicity;

– secondly, public opinion on the functioning of state governance entities;

– and thirdly, its broad consideration in the development of managerial decisions.

Publicity allows citizens to see the mechanism of formation and implementation of state governing influence and the course of all management processes.

Public opinion reflects the view (estimation, judgment) of the most active part of the population in terms of efficiency, utility, and correctness of management decisions. It is an array of information for state governance.

Consideration of public opinion is a channel of feedback in the system of state governance, use of the information array for the development and adoption of the most reasonable and effective governance decisions.

As S. Stetsenko notes, the manifestations of transparency principle are:

- a) openness and transparency of state bodies (officials and officers) in the exercise of their powers;
- b) essential role of the mass media in publicizing state governance decisions;
- c) everyone is guaranteed the right to free access and the right to distribute the information on the state of the environment, the quality of food products and household items. Such information can not be classified by anyone (Article 50 of the Constitution of Ukraine). In addition, citizens' access to information is regulated by the law "On Information" [8], "On Access to Public Information" [9], "On Information Protection in Information and Telecommunication Systems", and others like that.

The state ensures adherence to this principle in two ways:

– firstly, it requires state agencies to be transparent and open to the general public. Thus, the Law of Ukraine "On the Procedure for Covering the Activities of State and Local Authorities in Ukraine by Mass Media" states a norm which obliges these bodies to provide journalists with free access to information about their activities, as well as to provide it to mass media in full (Article 2);

– secondly, the state stimulates the right of the population to make judgments about the activities of public authorities and local self-government, as well as enterprises, institutions and organizations. Thus, the right of citizens of Ukraine to participate in the governance of state affairs (Article 38), encompassed in the Constitution, stipulates their awareness of the affairs in this sphere and encourages active actions aimed at its improvement. This norm is specified in the Law of Ukraine "On Appeal of Citizens" and other acts.

It should be noted that the livelihood of any social system destabilizes various challenges, dangers, threats, destroying them from the inside or outside. The social system performs a basic function of security for self-protection, i.e. it carries out security activities.

- 5) social governance as a kind of human activity.

3. Conclusions

So, as a conclusion, a conceptually new definition of the term "state guard" is suggested: "State guard is an activity carried out by a specially authorized state body in order to ensure the security of state authorities and officials determined by law on the basis of the application of the system of guarded, operative and search, organizational, legal, regime, technical, informational and other measures".

Thus, a state guard is a law enforcement activity, as well as the DSGU that is a law-enforcement agency of special purpose, a state body specially authorized permanently, on a professional basis and in accordance with the current legislation, to carry out state guard of state authorities and officials by means of prevention, detection and termination offenses in order to ensure security and normal functioning of the protected state authorities and officials, protection and defence of the rights and interests of citizens, society and state.

In view of the above, it can be stated that in the state governance system a state guard provided by the Department of State Guard of Ukraine is simultaneously a

security and law enforcement activity, namely, the agency has three legal statuses: a state security body, a law-enforcement body and a military formation.

References

1. Kolpakov V., Kuzmenko O. Administrative Law of Ukraine: Textbook. K.: Yurincom Inter, 2003. 544 p.
2. On Local Self-Government in Ukraine: Law of Ukraine dated May 21, 1997 // Vidomosti of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. 1997. No.24. Art.170.
3. Stetsenko S. Administrative Law of Ukraine: Textbook. K.: Atika, 2008. 624p.
4. Administrative Law of Ukraine [Textbook for law universities and faculties / Y. Bytiak, V. Bogutsky, V. Garashchuk, and others]; Edited by Bytiak. Kharkiv: Law, 2001. 528p.
5. The Constitution of Ukraine dated June 28, 1996 // Bulletin of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. 1996. No.30. Art. 141.
6. Code of Administrative Judicial Procedure of Ukraine dated July 6, 2005 // Bulletin of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. 2005. No. 35–36, No. 37. Art. 446.
7. On information: Law of Ukraine dated October 2, 1992 // Bulletin of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. 1992. No.48. Art. 650.
8. On Access to Public Information dated January 13, 2011 // Bulletin of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. 2011. No.32. Art.314.
9. On Data Protection in information and telecommunication systems: Law of Ukraine dated July 5, 1994 // Bulletin of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. 1994. No.31. Art.286.